

Assessing the Human Impacts on Nature in Bangladesh: Adoption of European *hemeroby* approach

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Abstract

The overall objective of the study was to assess the levels of human impacts on nature based on the European *hemeroby* approach in Bangladesh. Empirical data was used in this study. Based on the respondents' perceptions a set of parameters was developed and compiled in a matrix. Forest, vegetation, landscape and biodiversity were identified as the scale of naturalness. It was found that *ahemorobic* (disturbance-free) habitats are absent in Bangladesh. The natural forest remnants are highly degraded and fragmented. The probability of emerging natural successional forests is disappeared due to the massive destruction of natural regeneration. The natural landscape is degraded by unplanned urbanization and industrialization. Biodiversity is in peril due to natural habitat destruction, logging and poaching. The study advocated for a mitigation strategy to heal nature.

Keywords: *Hemeroby*, *ahemorobic*, naturalness, human disturbance, habitat destruction, unplanned urbanization, biodiversity, peril

Introduction

Nature conservation anchors a discourse that articulates a fusion of nature-culture-artificiality-stability-biodiversity. The concepts of human disturbances have been enjoying increasing popularity in the discussion of biodiversity conservation. Anthropogenic behaviour that harms nature" or "human activities contrary to nature" leads to unnatural conditions. The notions of pure naturalness are dogmatic and the present environmental conditions are the products of a plethora of human disturbances. Human activities are the result of the evolution of other life forms in the biosphere. The Homo Faber ("man the maker") plays the most significant role in the highly complex manipulations of nature.

The term *hemeroby* derives from the Greek *hemeros* (cultivated, modified and disturbed) and this work is not found in the English dictionary. At first a Finnish botanist Jalas, J. (1955) introduced this term in ecology to classify the plant species based on their share in neophytic species. Sukopp, H. (1966) expanded this term to measure the degree of naturalness and human impact on the environment. Another German ecologist Kowarik, I. (1990) defined *hemeroby* as "the sum of the effects of past and present human activities on the current site conditions or vegetation, which prevent the development to a final stage".

Europe has developed two main concepts for assessing the human impacts on habitats and vegetation: 1) historical concept (comparison of vegetation and habitat with pristine nature/untouched nature) and 2) status-quo oriented concept (This is the *hemeroby* concept, which assesses the human impacts and naturalness of a site without a reference to former conditions). It is obvious to have knowledge of the improvable "primal condition" of nature to define "naturalness", "close to nature" "unnaturalness" and "human impacts" per historical concept. In this concept, "back to nature" means no more return than the pre-human (unknown) condition of nature; The *hemeroby* concept has the advantage of excluding the dogma of purely natural (pre-human and unknown) conditions. A *hemeroby* approach is an essential tool for ecological analysis.

The levels of *hemeroby* are measured based on the proportion of neophytic and therophytic species, soil characteristics and land use patterns. There are seven levels of *hemeroby* which

determine the degree of human impact on a specific landscape (Zinnen *et al.* 2020). The *hemeroby* scale depends on vegetation coverage and the properties of habitats. Natural plant communities are sensitive to changes in the *hemeroby* scale (intensity of anthropopression).

Vacik *et al.* (2009) and Rahman *et al.* (2008) assessed the dynamics of Oak dominated natural forest reserves of Central Europe. It was found 12.8% stand volume and 8.6% deadwood (an indicator of naturalness) volume increased in 10-year pure natural conditions. Those natural reserves are *ahemorobic* (disturbance-free) habitats, which is an illusion in Bangladesh.

The natural habitats of Bangladesh are degrading day by day (Rahman 2021). The levels of human impacts have never been determined in our country. A few studies measured the human impacts on the biodiversity of Bangladesh giving attention to the floristic composition and species richness, and ignoring the habitat and landscape conditions (Rahman 2023; Rahman 2022, a; Rahman 2009; Rahman *et al.* 2007, Rahman *et al.* 2009, Rahman and Vacik 2009, 2010). The study aimed to develop a disturbance index based on the diverse disturbance gradients and baseline of *hemeroby* assessment in Bangladesh.

Methodology

Empirical data was used for this study. A focus group discussion was done incorporating the respondents from diverse stakeholders. A total number of 10 key respondents were interviewed to a set of parameters. Content analysis was done to quantify the qualitative value of each parameter. The quantified data was compiled in a matrix to assess the different levels of *hemeroby*.

How to use it in Bangladesh?

To measure the scale of *hemeroby* it took qualitative and quantitative assessments of human impacts on the flora and habitats. It was argued that quantitative assessment was highly complex and costly. The qualitative assessment was understandable and cost-effective as in Bangladesh.

Based on the respondents' perceptions a set of parameters was developed for assessing *hemeroby* in Bangladesh (Figure 1). The parameters were identified based on different landscapes, ecosystems, human impacts and habitat conditions.

Figure 1: A set of parameters for assessing *hemeroby* in Bangladesh

The qualitative value of each parameter was compiled in a matrix for assessing the different levels of *hemeroby* (Figure 2).

Figure 2: A matrix of different parameters

Most European countries use the *hemeroby* to study the dynamics of plant communities in urban areas and to assess the human disturbances in different habitats. It describes the spectrum of severity of human impact on any particular plant community.

How to heal nature in Bangladesh?

Based on *hemeroby* assessments the following conservation strategies can be adopted:

- a) establishing at least 01-hectare pure natural habitat within each protected forest to promote *ahemerobic* conditions, which will serve the reference value of naturalness;
- b) building a bridge between humans and nature by removing the ideology from and the demystification of the phenomena of nature and humans;
- c) pragmatic-sustainable development;
- d) maintaining equilibrium between the stability and sustainable productivity of the environment;
- e) adopting scientifically and economically congenial strategies for biodiversity conservation;
- f) protecting habitat, landscape, and biodiversity to attain the goals that were outlined in the "Convention on Biodiversity";
- g) ecosystem management through the participation of all stakeholders;
- h) creating public relations for nature conservation;
- i) minimizing the use of chemical fertilizers;
- j) prohibiting the application of long residual and acute toxic pesticides;
- k) protecting habitat fragmentation;
- l) increasing urban vegetation;
- m) establishing the more botanical parks in each city and town;
- n) minimising soil pollution;
- o) afforestation, reforestation and vegetation in the denuded area;

p) stopping clear felling;

q) eco-friendly garbage management.

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